

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PAIN SCREENING IN THE DELIRIOUS PATIENT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2016

ABSTRACT

Poorly managed pain hastens death in the frail geriatric population. The development of delirium is one of the most common hospital-acquired diagnoses in the acute care geriatric setting, contributing to increased mortality rates, extended hospitalizations, and greater hospital expenditures. Insufficiently managed pain contributes to delirium development. In order to reduce the incidence of delirium, proper pain screening must be pursued. In this project, the efficiency of the Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia (PAIN-AD) scale for pain screening was evaluated among acutely hospitalized delirious patients within an urban academic setting. In this observational case control study of 36 nonverbal delirious acute care patients, two trained bedside providers identified behavioral indicators of pain through the use of two tools for pain screening (the PAIN-AD and the Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool [CPOT]). Patients were provided with an intervention when the PAIN-AD score was 3 or greater or the CPOT score was 2 or greater. Patients were reassessed after 30 minutes. The mean age of patients was 86.14 years ($SD = 8.49$; range 65-96); of the sample, 19 (54.3%) were women, 27 (75.0%) were White, and 25 (69.4%) had a history of dementia. The PAIN-AD and CPOT interrater reliability (intraclass correlations two-way, random) was found to be excellent (0.99), as was internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha at baseline = 0.80-0.83 and at follow-up = 0.81-0.87). Construct validity was supported by observation of a multi-trait matrix. However, examination of pain scores over time for patients with and

without a pain intervention did not show the expected finding of decreased pain using the PAIN-AD. Because the reductions in pain were trending towards statistical significance ($p = .06$), post hoc power analyses were done; six to ten additional subjects would have been needed to detect the observed reductions in pain as statistically significant. These results generally suggest that pain screening in the nonverbal delirious acutely hospitalized geriatric population can be conducted with the PAIN-AD. However, further studies are warranted, as the sample size for this study was small and homogeneous and some measures of construct validity failed to reach significance at the 0.05 level.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to acknowledge my chair, Dr. Goebel, and my Co-Chair, Dr. Gorman, for all of their hard work and dedication guiding me through this tedious process. I would like to express my sincere appreciation to Dr. Matesic and Jeannie Meyer for their suggestions during the conduction of this study. I have been fortunate enough to have many mentors throughout my career assisting in my professional development.

Assistance provided by Ashwini Prasad was of great help for facilitating the collection of data. Many special thanks to the nursing staff at Santa Monica UCLA on both the 5 North Wing Tower and 5 Merle Norman Pavilion where this study was conducted for their assistance completing interventions when warranted. I am deeply appreciative to the participants who participated in this study.

A special thank you to my parents, Lesley and Michael Ferolito, who inspire me to be better on a daily basis. Parents instill an unwavering dedication in their children, one that I have been fortunate to be privy to throughout the course of my life. Finally, thank you to my aunt Brenda DeVellis who assisted with formulating my thoughts for this project.

BACKGROUND

Treating pain in a geriatric acute care setting can be challenging due to the intensity of the environment and the shifting priorities of staff, resulting in pain underrecognition (Coyle, Breitbart, Weaver, & Portenoy, 1994; B. A. Ferrell & Ferrell, 1995; Morrison et al., 2003). A painful condition in an older person contributes to a reduced quality of life (Brown, 2004; Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2007). Throughout the literature, pain is listed as a contributing factor to the development of delirium (Coyle et al., 1994; Morrison et al., 2003). Delirium is one of the most frequently diagnosed conditions in geriatric patients (Ryan et al., 2013). It is estimated that one in every five patients is found to be delirium positive in the hospital setting, and those with a history of cognitive impairment have the highest propensity for delirium development (Laurila, Pitkala, Strandberg, & Tilvis, 2002; Ryan et al., 2013). Although there is an association between pain and delirium, there have been few studies to investigate the best screening methods for pain in acutely hospitalized geriatric patients.

The treatment units where the author practices serve a diverse geriatric participant population where both pain and delirium are common occurrences. Research suggests that effective pain management is associated with decreased hospital stays and healthcare expenditures (McCaffery, Pasero, & Ferrell, 2010). While the identification and alleviation of pain in cognitively impaired participants poses challenges, nursing continues to strive to improve pain screening in this vulnerable population (B. R. Ferrell & Coyle, 2010). When pain is identified appropriately, interventions can be initiated to facilitate the appropriate management of pain. Effective pain management can reduce

delirium in the hospitalized geriatric patient, as pain is a factor that has been proven to contribute to the diagnosis of delirium (Morrison et al., 2003).

Problem Statement

Physical pain is a common symptom associated with acute and chronic illnesses as well as with ageing (Chatterjee, 2012). While a variety of studies have validated pain-screening methods in participants with dementia (Herr, Bjoro, & Decker, 2006), there is limited information about pain screening in the delirious participant population. The Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia (PAIN-AD) tool uses nonverbal measures to screen for pain in participants with dementia (Bjoro & Herr, 2008). Another common pain screening tool, the Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool (CPOT), has been validated in critical care settings with nonverbal intubated participants (Gélinas, Harel, Fillion, Puntillo, & Johnston, 2009). The question of whether the PAIN-AD effectively screens for pain in participants who exhibit delirium remains unanswered.

Although several tools are available to identify delirium in the acute care setting (Inouye et al., 1990), the Confusion Assessment Method (CAM) may be the most frequently cited tool in the literature (Laurila et al., 2002; Waszynski, 2012). The CAM is available in several languages and demonstrates consistent reliability, supporting its transferability across ethnicities (Institute for Aging Research, 2014). By evaluating the pain tools (the PAIN-AD and CPOT) used in current clinical practice at the Santa Monica UCLA (University of California, Los Angeles; SMUCLA) Medical Center, the author plans on generating evidence on pain screening in her setting.

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to evaluate the efficacy of the PAIN-AD for pain screening in a population of delirious participants in an urban academic setting. The PAIN-AD tool was compared to the CPOT in this setting in an effort to evaluate the PAIN-AD's validity to identify pain in this population. The importance of pain screening in delirium is great; with appropriate interventions for pain, causes can be identified and the deleterious sequelae of pain mitigated.

Project Objectives

The objective of this study was to measure the reliability of the PAIN-AD scale for use in an acute care delirious patient population. There was additionally a comparison of the PAIN-AD scale to the CPOT for the purpose of evaluating the PAIN-AD scale's validity.

Supporting Framework

The Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) curriculum educates students to identify gaps in knowledge and initiate and evaluate practice changes to improve participant experiences. The logic model is a systematic way to guide practice change. It provides a roadmap to evaluate connections between planned work and intended results (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). The logic model is often used as a management tool, as it enables stakeholders to reassess information as a project progresses for ongoing program improvement. There are five steps in the logic model: resources/inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact (see Figure 1). The author used the logic model to create a blueprint for articulation of who has been involved throughout the course of this study

Figure 1. Logic model.

and what has been done in the study to identify a priori measurable outcomes. Identifying specific project benchmarks facilitated buy-in from administrators and bedside staff.

Inputs/Resources

This DNP project used resources both within and outside the acute care setting of practice. There was a collaborative partnership with the chief nursing officer at the SMUCLA Medical Center, the staff on the acute care geriatric unit, the medical team on the geriatric service, the palliative care clinical nurse specialist (CNS), and the statistician at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). Approval from the geriatric service at the SMUCLA Medical Center was sought, as they are responsible for the medical care of the participants within these units. The nursing staff was involved in all phases of the

project, as they were essential for identifying participants appropriate for the study. The nursing staff's time is valuable, as they are very busy providing complex, time intensive participant care. A research assistant was designated for data collection purposes, acting as an essential member of the study team. The palliative care CNS was in agreement with the objectives of the project and assisted in the administration of the plan. The statistician at CSUF provided advice on project design, assisted in data analysis and interpretation, and calculated the results and discussion sections of the manuscript.

Outputs—Activities

The activities that were used to accomplish outcomes included a review of current pain management practices and policies at the SMUCLA Medical Center. There were weekly meetings with the palliative care CNS and research assistant to identify gaps in pain practices. Participant charts were reviewed, after approval was received from the Institutional Review Boards (IRBs), to identify CAM positive (+) participants. The PAIN-AD and CPOT were completed at the bedside by two assessors (one research bedside provider and the author also a bedside provider) and their assessments have been compared for interrater reliability. Participants who screened positive for pain received nursing interventions and were reassessed 30 minutes after the intervention by both registered nurses.

Outputs—Participation

The administrators and the bedside nursing staff on the geriatric and step-down units actively participated in the planning and completion of this project. A nursing staff member interesting in research assisted in data collection. Approval was received from

her unit supervisor for 4 paid hours of work weekly. The dignity of the participants and families was maintained through all screening and rescreening periods.

Outcomes—Impact

The short-term outcomes included an enhanced awareness of pain screening in participants with delirium. There was improvement in the pain screening skills of the nursing staff as they received education by the author throughout the project.

The medium-term outcomes included improved attitudes of the nursing staff toward the value of pain screening. Pain management improved. This project generated evidence related to efficient pain screening methods for delirious participants. A publishable manuscript and podium presentation will be completed one year after the completion of the project.

The long-term effects of project completion will lead to overall improvements in participant care. The cost of care per participant may decrease, as appropriate pain management could decrease hospital length of stay. Participants with appropriately managed pain will be more comfortable. Participant satisfaction and family satisfaction would increase. The nursing staff will feel empowered, as they will be active participants in the process of improving participant care. The project could lead to practice changes throughout the hospital.

Conclusion

The logic model is an organized approach to enhance the planning and evaluation of this DNP project. It has an extensive history of supporting quality improvement projects and program evaluations (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). Clearly articulating

outcomes both in the short term and long term has and will ensure greater support from administrators.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Literature on pain screening in the delirium population is lacking. Tools exist for the screening of delirium itself; however, there is not a clear gold standard established for pain identification in the delirious participant. Although information exists on the need for stringent pain control in postoperative surgical participants to decrease delirium (Brown, 2004; Morrison et al., 2003; Vaurio, Sands, Wang, Mullen, & Leung, 2006), there is little literature about the non-post-surgical acute care geriatric population. The following review of the literature seeks to validate the use of the CAM in the acute care setting for delirium identification. Two pain screening tools for nonverbal cognitively impaired participants have been reviewed in an effort to identify tools to potentiate better practice for this delicate population.

Overview: Pain Screening in the Cognitively Impaired Population

As early as 1995, B. A. Ferrell and Ferrell published a seminal paper describing the challenge of addressing pain in the cognitively impaired population. Some of the barriers associated with insufficient pain management included poor screening and documentation of pain by workers in the skilled nursing facility setting (B. A. Ferrell & Ferrell, 1995). The inability of cognitively impaired participants to appropriately communicate their discomfort levels is often difficult to characterize secondary to memory, language, and speech deficits and consciousness alterations (Buffman, Hutt, Chang, Craine, & Snow, 2007). Nearly 20 years ago, pain management in this population was demanded to be a priority (Parmelee, 1997). As the geriatric population increases to an estimated 83.7 million by 2050 (Ortman, Velkoff, & Hogan, 2014), the question of pain control becomes increasingly more relevant. In order to address pain in this

vulnerable population, valid and reliable tools are necessary for nurses to screen for pain. The next sections of this literature review will summarize what is currently known about the tools that will be used in this DNP project.

CAM

Delirium is one of the most frequent complications endured by the elderly during acute hospitalization (Inouye, 2006; Rice et al., 2011; Waszynski, 2012). The detection of delirium remains variable due to a lack of knowledge on premorbid level of cognition (Martins, Conceição, Paiva, Simões, & Fernandes, 2014). Delirium healthcare-associated costs range from \$38 to \$152 billion annually (Leslie, Marcantonio, Zhang, Leo-Summers, & Inouye, 2008). The CAM was developed in 1990 and has since been identified as a best practice tool due to its reliability and ease of use (Waszynski, 2012). The identification and treatment of delirium early in a participant's hospital course can dramatically affect his or her overall outcome and decrease mortality (Friedman, Qin, Berkenstadt, & Katznelson, 2008; Ryan et al., 2013; Waszynski & Petrovic, 2008).

The CAM is the most widely used and accepted screening tool for delirium in acute care practice (Laurila et al., 2002; Lemiengre et al., 2006; Rice et al., 2011; Waszynski & Petrovic, 2008). There are some gaps that remain to be seen in the literature. For example, staff nurses, although proficient at knowing when delirium is not present, appear to poorly differentiate symptoms when it is present (Rice et al., 2011). Without a fundamental understanding on how to use the CAM, a positive identification of delirium cannot be made. Additional education is necessary for all staff nurses using the CAM. If a participant tests positive for delirium by the CAM, additional diagnostic

criteria in accordance with the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM)* criteria should be sought (Kakuma et al., 2003; Waszynski, 2012).

PAIN-AD

Pain is difficult to assess in participants who have a diagnosis of cognitive impairment due to their inability to self-report (Buffman et al., 2007). The PAIN-AD is a tool that was developed by Victoria Warden in 2003 to better detect and treat pain in the dementia population through behavioral indicators of pain (Warden, Hurley, & Volicer, 2003).

There is a need for further studies utilizing the PAIN-AD in acute care and nursing home settings for further validation of its use (Esrek, Herr, Neradilek, Buck, & Black, 2010; Jordan, Regnard, O'Brien, & Hughes, 2012; Warden et al., 2003). The PAIN-AD may be most effective at detecting pain after participant movement (Esrek et al., 2010). Another tool to assess distress, or the creation of a tool bundle, could potentially increase the specificity of the PAIN-AD. Pain is a multifactorial phenomenon that must be addressed appropriately to decrease distress in geriatric participants (Jordan et al., 2012). Poorly managed pain can result in adverse physical and psychological outcomes for participants (Wells, Pasero, & McCaffery, 2008). Delirium, considered a complex neuropsychiatric syndrome (Ryan et al., 2013), has subtle similarities to dementia. The use of the PAIN-AD in delirium participants could reveal subtle behavioral differences in pain presentation.

CPOT

Pain self-report has been identified as the gold standard of pain measurement (Horgas & Elliot, 2012). The CPOT was developed by Celine Gélinas for participants in

the critical care setting who were not able to verbally advocate for themselves due to conditions such as intubation, sedative use, and fluctuating mental status (Gélinas, Fillion, Puntillo, Viens, & Fortier, 2006). Validation studies for the CPOT have been conducted primarily in the intensive care unit (ICU) setting and have evaluated participants who are intubated and unable to self-report after nociceptive procedures such as turning (Gélinas et al., 2006; Gélinas, Harel, Fillion, Puntillo, & Johnston, 2009; Gélinas & Johnston, 2007).

Tousignant-Laflamme, Bourgault, Gélinas, and Marchand (2010) postulated using the CPOT in different settings in an effort to expand its generalizability to other practice settings. The consensus of the reviewed studies reveals that a CPOT score of greater than 2 warrants an intervention (Gélinas et al., 2009). Using the CPOT in other practice settings within hospitals could potentially be of value for participants who are not verbally able to communicate their pain levels, as it evaluates four pain-related nonverbal behaviors. As it is possible the CPOT will be more reliable in the acute care setting than the PAIN-AD, this DNP project will formally compare these two tools.

Literature Search

A thorough literature review search in CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar identified relevant research on methods to screen for delirium as well as pain screening tools used in geriatric populations. Inclusion criteria included English language only, 2002-2015 (with a focus on 2010-2015), populations 65 and older, and peer reviewed. Key terms included pain, delirium, CAM, PAIN-AD, CPOT, geriatric, elderly, and older adults.

The keywords used to identify literature on delirium screening tools in geriatric participants included *elderly*, *older adults*, *geriatric*, and *CAM*. CINAHL provided the most studies as this database directly relates to the field of nursing. When searching the keyword *CAM*, 3,594 titles were identified. When *CAM geriatrics older adults elderly* was used, there were 116 titles. With Google Scholar, a similar search sequence was completed. Initially, 3,770,000 titles were identified when *CAM* was used and when *delirium screening* was added, 40,600 titles were identified. Another search using the keywords *CAM*, *screening*, and *geriatrics* identified 21,200 titles; 191 of these articles were published in the current year.

For the second topic, pain screening tools, the keywords *PAIN-AD*, *pain*, *elderly*, and *geriatric* were used. One title was identified in CINAHL with the term *PAIN-AD*, and 2,214 titles were identified with the keywords *pain* and *screening*. Another search with the terms *pain*, *screening*, and *elderly people* identified 79 titles. A Google Scholar search with the term *PAIN-AD tool* identified 49 titles. A third search for titles related to the *CPOT* identified 33 titles in PubMed and 27 titles in CINAHL. The most pertinent studies for the purposes of this project are listed in the Table of Evidence (Appendix A).

METHODS

An observational case control study design was used to achieve the objectives of this study. A sample of 36 nonverbal delirious acute care participants were observed by two trained nurses (the author and a research assistant) to identify behavioral indicators of pain through using the PAIN-AD and CPOT tools for pain screening. Participants who appeared to be in pain, as identified by the screening tools, received an intervention (repositioning, heat application, medication administration) and a rescreening was done 30 minutes thereafter to identify if the intervention was effective. Participants who did not screen positive for behavioral indicators of pain were used as a control group and also reevaluated after 30 minutes.

Sample/Setting

This project enrolled 36 participants in both the acute care geriatric unit and the step-down telemetry unit (capacity 26 and 36 participants, respectively) at the SMUCLA Medical Center. Participants were included in this study if they were 65 years of age or older, unable to state a pain score, and were CAM+. Participants were excluded if they were younger than 65 years of age, able to state a pain score, and were CAM negative (-).

Measures

Data Abstraction Tool

A paper-and-pencil data abstraction tool was created to record demographic and clinical variables of interest from the electronic health record. The following data elements were abstracted and recorded on the tool: (a) CAM score, (b) procedure with anesthesia use within 48 hours, (c) presence and location of infection (e.g., blood, urine),

(d) benzodiazepine use, (e) name, (f) admission diagnosis, (g) age, (h) gender, (i) sex, (j) ethnicity/race, and (k) length of stay at the time of pain screening.

CAM

The CAM uses four factors to identify the presence of delirium: (a) acute onset and fluctuating course, (b) inattention, (c) disorganized thinking, and (d) altered level of consciousness (Inouye et al., 1990). After a review of the factors, a participant is given a positive or a negative score. A positive diagnosis of delirium is established through reviewing the diagnostic algorithm, which defines delirium as consisting of the presence of factors 1 (acute onset) and 2 (inattention) and either of the remaining factors 3 or 4 (disorganized thinking or altered level of consciousness). Wei, Fearing, Sternberg, and Inouye (2008), in a systematic review of the CAM, analyzed seven studies and established an overall sensitivity of 94% and specificity of 89% for the diagnosis of delirium.

PAIN-AD

Two pain tools were used to screen for pain: the PAIN-AD tool (Warden et al., 2003) and the CPOT (Gélinas & Arbour, 2009). Both tools are currently included in the nursing pain screening policy at the SMUCLA Medical Center. The PAIN-AD evaluates five behaviors: breathing, negative vocalization, facial expression, body language, and consolability. Each behavior is scored from 0 to 2.

Scores on each of the five behaviors are summed for a total score. A total score of 1-3 indicates mild pain, a score of 4-6 indicates moderate pain, and a score of 7-10 indicates severe pain (Warden et al., 2003). The PAIN-AD was compared to the DS-DAT tool in dementia participants (Warden et al., 2003). These authors observed participants

on three occasions: during pleasant activity or rest, during unpleasant activity, and after as needed medication administration. Internal consistency (reliability) between assessors was also measured and found to be 0.70 (Warden et al., 2003).

CPOT

The CPOT screens participants for pain for 1 minute at rest and then during nociceptive procedures (e.g., turning); the highest score warrants an intervention. The tool includes screenings related to the participant's facial expression, body movements, vocalization, and muscle tension; each item is scored from 0 to 2. A total score of 2 or more is significant for pain and merits interventions. The participant should then be assessed before and at the peak of analgesic medications to identify the tools effectiveness in that the expectation would be to see a reduction in pain (score) after interventions are pursued (Gélinas et al., 2009).

Gélinas et al. (2009) evaluated the sensitivity and specificity of the CPOT in critically-ill ventilated participants after cardiac surgery. The results of the study revealed a sensitivity of 86% and specificity of 78% after a nociceptive procedure. At rest, the specificity was 83%-97%, though the tool had a lower sensitivity of 47%-63%. Although the CPOT has only been validated in the critical care setting, previous work suggests that the behavior measures can translate to any population with the exception of ventilated participants (Tousignant-Laflamme et al., 2010).

Procedures

Prior to the initiation of the project, the author and a trained research assistant (bedside provider) reviewed modules on both Warden et al.'s (2003) PAIN-AD scale and Gélinas and Johnston's (2007) CPOT pain scales for one 2-hour session. Training on the

use of the PAIN-AD was completed using the Hartford Institute's "Try This" series (Waszynski, 2012). A review of the CPOT was completed through viewing the free video created by Kaiser Permanente of Northern California on its appropriate use. The CAM will not be reviewed in great detail, as this screening is already done on every participant on the acute care geriatric unit and step-down unit as part of normal practices and the nursing staff have received extensive training on its proper use. Approval for the use of the CAM, PAIN-AD, and CPOT was sought from the authors (Appendix B-D).

The nursing staff on the geriatric nursing and step-down units were informed of the study through fliers posted throughout the units (Appendix E). An email was sent by the management of the units 1 month prior to the initiation of the study to inform the staff of the study and to enhance overall staff awareness. The author identified participants by asking individual nurses on an acute care telemetry geriatric medical-surgical unit (5 North Wing) and an acute care step-down telemetry unit (5 Merle Norman) for the names of the CAM+ participants who were unable to verbalize a pain score (Appendix F). Two bedside providers acted as data collectors (the author and a nurse research assistant) reviewed the electronic health record for inclusion criteria as well as the participant's ability to verbalize a pain score. If the participant qualified for the project, a unique seven-character identification number (month, date, year of enrollment in the project, and a sequential letter) was placed on each data extraction tool (Appendix G). Clinical and demographic information—CAM score, pain history, anesthesia use within 48 hours, presence and location of infection (e.g., blood, urine), benzodiazepine use, age, gender, name, ethnicity, race, and length of stay at the time of pain screening—was recorded on

the tool. This was the only information that was placed onto the data collection tool to ensure confidentiality.

Each of the nurses (data collectors) went to the bedside of CAM+ participants to independently assess the participant's pain level using the PAIN-AD and CPOT; they entered the room in synchrony and then stood on separate ends of the participant's room for each screening. Each nurse had the exact same data recording tool and independently assessed and recorded baseline scores for each participant. After each independent screening, the nurses compared scores. After comparing scores, if a difference in scores greater than 2 was noted, a final score was agreed upon by consensus of two geriatric experts and one palliative care CNS and recorded on both paper-and-pencil tools.

The participant's primary nurse was alerted if the PAIN-AD score was equal to or greater than 2 (indicating at least moderate pain) or the CPOT score was equal to or greater than 2 (indicating need for intervention; Gélinas & Johnston, 2007; Tousignant-Laflamme et al., 2010). For participants with a PAIN-AD score of less than 2 or a CPOT score of 1 (mild pain), no intervention was provided. For participants with a PAIN-AD score equal to or greater than 2 or CPOT score of equal to or greater than 2, the participant's primary nurse provided an appropriate intervention including a positional change, heat application, or analgesic administration (per physician orders or nursing judgment). The data collectors went to the participant's bedside 30 minutes after the intervention or baseline screening and re-screened the scores for both the nonintervention and the intervention participants.

All data were collected by paper and pencil and then entered into an Excel spreadsheet on a desktop computer at the SMUCLA Medical Center. The abstracted data

and pain screenings remained with the author at all times or were stored in a locked file drawer in a locked office at the SMUCLA Medical Center. Only the author and research assistant obtained a key to the drawer and to the office. The data from the paper-and-pencil tool were transferred by the author into an Excel spreadsheet on a password protected computer in the CNS office. The Excel spreadsheet information was transferred into SPSS with only numbers as sample indicators. The SPSS spreadsheet was sent through email for analysis to the statistician and the author's chair. Only the author, her chair, and the statistician had access to the de-identified data. All paper or electronic records are to be destroyed by the SMUCLA Medical Center, according to their protocol, 3 years after the completion of the project. After study completion, overwriting will destroy all electronic records.

Study Approval

The IRBs at the SMUCLA Medical Center and CSULB and the Nursing Research Practice Counsel at the SMUCLA Medical Center approved this project (Appendix H-J).

Analysis

All data were imported into SPSS version 21 for analysis, and GLIMMPSE was utilized for power analyses. The following analyses were completed:

1. Face validity for the PAIN-AD was evaluated through having three experts in geriatrics and pain examine the suitability of the tool for the population under study.
2. Interrater reliability scores (intraclass correlations [ICC] two-way, random) were computed for the PAIN-AD and the COPT (both pre and postintervention).

3. For the nonintervention group, test-retest reliability was calculated via bivariate correlations between baseline scores on the tools (CPOT and PAIN-AD) and scores obtained 30 minutes after baseline.
4. Internal consistency (reliability) of the tools was examined through calculation of Cronbach's alpha for the PAIN-AD and the CPOT.
5. Concurrent (construct) validity was examined by reviewing the scores between the CPOT and the PAIN-AD at baseline (e.g., if the PAIN-AD was high, the CPOT would be expected to be high as well).
6. Construct validity of the tool was examined via a 2x2 repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) examining PAIN-AD scores (baseline vs. 30 minutes postintervention) between the two conditions (intervention vs. nonintervention). A statistically significant decrease in postintervention PAIN-AD scores in the intervention group only would support the internal validity of the tool.
7. Due to nonsignificant findings, a pair of a posteriori power analyses were conducted at the completion of the project to examine the necessary sample size for future research.

PUBLISHABLE MANUSCRIPT

PAIN SCREENING IN THE DELIRIOUS PATIENT

Introduction

In the frail elderly population, unaddressed pain may hasten death through physiological means such as diminishing immunocompetence and increasing the workload of the heart and respiratory systems (Paice, 2015). Unfortunately, evidence is lacking in the best approaches to screen for pain in cognitively impaired (specifically delirious), acute care patients (B. R. Ferrell & Coyle, 2010; McCaffery, Pasero, & Ferrell, 2010). Thus, the purpose of this study is to provide psychometric evidence of the efficacy of the Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia (PAIN-AD) tool for pain screening in a geriatric acute care population with delirium.

The challenges of screening for pain in cognitively impaired patients are well documented (B. A. Ferrell & Ferrell, 1995). With the aging population, the prevalence of cognitive impairment will be increasing (Coyle, Breitbart, Weaver, & Portenoy, 1994; B. A. Ferrell & Ferrell, 1995; Morrison et al., 2003). Delirium, an acute reversible form of cognitive impairment, is common in hospitalized geriatric patient and may result from untreated pain (Laurila, Pitkala, Strandberg, & Tilvis, 2002; Ryan et al., 2013; Wells, Pasero, & McCaffery, 2008). Many patients suffering with delirium are unable to self-report pain and providers must use tools for pain-screening that assess behavioral indicators of pain such as grimacing and moaning. The PAIN-AD, a commonly used tool for pain screening in delirious populations, had its psychometric qualities evaluated in long-term care settings with dementia patients. Thus this study breaks new ground by

investigating the reliability and validity of the PAIN-AD in an acute care setting with delirious geriatric patients.

Methods

Design and Sample

An observational case control study design was used to achieve the objectives of this study. In an urban tertiary acute care setting, two researchers screened 36 nonverbal delirious patients with the PAIN-AD and the Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool (CPOT). Patients were included if they were Confusion Assessment Method (CAM)+, 65 years of age or older, and unable to state a pain score. The Santa Monica UCLA (University of California, Los Angeles; SMUCLA) Medical Center and California State University, Long Beach, Institutional Review Boards and the SMUCLA Medical Center Nursing Research Practice Counsel provided approvals for this study.

Study Procedures

Preceding the initiation of the study, the two bedside providers completed training modules (2 hours total) related to the PAIN-AD and CPOT scales. A clinical nurse specialist with expertise in pain management and palliative care reviewed the tools with the researchers to ensure consistent application of the tools. Staff was informed of the study through an email announcement from the unit's management 4 weeks prior to study initiation. Medical-surgical units posted flyers in common areas announcing the study. Bedside nurses reported patients who were CAM+, unable to state pain levels, and 65 years of age or older to the researchers.

Researchers assessed baseline behavioral indicators of pain with the PAIN-AD and CPOT. If the PAIN-AD score was 3 or greater or the CPOT score was 2 or greater,

the researcher would alert the bedside nurse to turn the patient, provide heat therapy, or provide an analgesic. Approximately 30 minutes after baseline assessments, another assessment was completed. The study took place over a 12-week period in 2015.

Measures

Demographic and clinical data was abstracted from the electronic health record with a standardized tool.

CAM. The CAM is the most widely used screening tool for delirium in acute care practice (Laurila et al., 2002; Lemiengre et al., 2006; Rice et al., 2011; Waszynski & Petrovic, 2008). A positive diagnosis of delirium occurs when the cognitive impairment occurs acutely, there is the presence of inattention, and the patient has either disorganized thinking or altered level of consciousness (Inouye et al., 1990).

PAIN-AD. The PAIN-AD tool screens dementia patients through five behavioral measures of pain: breathing, negative vocalization, facial expression, body language, and consolability. Each behavior is scored from 0 (the absence of pain) to 2 (the highest ranking score per behavior) and are summed for a total score which ranges from 0-10. The tool was validated in the convalescent home setting with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 exhibiting fair reliability (Warden, Hurley, & Volicer, 2003).

CPOT. The CPOT assesses behavioral indicators of pain including the patient's facial expression, body movements, vocalization, and muscle tension; each item is scored from 0 (no pain) to 2 (the most pain per behavior). A total score of 2 or more is significant for pain and merits interventions (Gélinas & Arbour, 2009). In a critical care setting, intraclass correlation coefficients 0.80 to 0.93 suggests strong interrater reliability, and test retest reliability.

Statistical Analysis

All initial analyses were completed through IBM SPSS version 21. GLIMMPSE was used to conduct a posteriori power analyses.

Results

Study Population

Thirty-six participants were enrolled in this study. Participants were predominantly White ($n = 27, 75.0\%$), with a fairly equal dispersion of males ($n = 16, 45.7\%$) to females ($n = 19, 54.3\%$). The mean age of participants was 86.14 years ($SD = 8.4$). Most participants ($n = 30, 85.7\%$) had not received benzodiazepines or anticholinergic medications. The most common admitting diagnoses were altered level of consciousness ($n = 6, 16.7\%$) and sepsis ($n = 4, 11.1\%$). Dementia and infection diagnoses were common among participants ($n = 25, 69.4\%$ and $n = 11, 45.7\%$, respectively). The mean length of stay for participants was 5 days ($SD = 4.5$). Fifteen ($n = 15, 41.0\%$) had a history of any painful diagnosis. Mean PAIN-AD score at baseline were 2.93 (range 0-10, $SD = 2.84$) and mean CPOT score was 2.21 (range 0-8, $SD = 2.38$). Twenty patients (55.6%) had PAIN-AD scores 3 or greater or CPOT scores 2 or greater and received a pain intervention (see Table 1).

PAIN-AD

In order to examine the psychometric properties of PAIN-AD scale, Cronbach's alpha, 30-minute test-retest reliability (Pearson product-moment correlation), and interrater reliability (ICC[2,k]) were calculated (see Table 2).

PAIN-AD: Internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the PAIN-AD revealed strong internal consistency (0.80-0.87).

PAIN-AD: Reliability. Interrater reliability was excellent at baseline and after 30 minutes (0.99), illustrating the feasibility of implementing the tool in this work setting. Similarly, test-retest reliability showed relatively stable scores over time in the control group. For participants without pain, test-retest scores reflected adequate reliability (0.72-0.73).

PAIN-AD: Validity. Validity of the PAIN-AD was established by examination of the scale's face validity, calculation of a multitrait matrix, and examinations of mean scores by condition and time. In regard to face validity, a panel of experts in pain management ($n = 3$) at our institution reviewed the tool for face validity and found it to be excellent.

Examination of the item correlations between the PAIN-AD and CPOT via a multitrait matrix revealed promising findings, with fairly high correlations both between the PAIN-AD's individual questions as well as between the PAIN-AD's and the CPOT's questions, supporting the construct validity of the PAIN-AD (see Table 3).

However, a repeated measures 2x2 analysis of variance (ANOVA) failed to detect a statistically significant interaction effect between time (pretest vs. posttest) and condition (pain intervention group vs. control group), Rater 1: $F(1,31) = 3.79, p = .06$, and Rater 2: $F(1,30) = 3.83, p = .06$. A statistically significant decrease in pain over time in the intervention group was theoretically expected and thus used as a condition for establishing construct validity.

PAIN-AD: Power analysis. Because statistically significant interaction effects between time (preintervention vs. postintervention) and intervention (pain intervention vs. control) were not observed despite a theoretical rationale expecting scores to decrease

over time in the pain intervention group only and data matching the expected pattern (see Figures 2 and 3), it was decided to conduct a series of power analyses to determine the sample size that would have been needed in order to have an 80% chance of finding the observed interactions to be statistically significant. Because of the difficulties inherent in conducting power analyses in repeated measures analyses (Guo, Logan, Glueck, & Muller, 2013), it was decided to run power analyses in GLIMMPSE using the parameters observed in the repeated measures ANOVAs.

Using the parameters (M , SD , correlations, etc.) from the analysis of Rater 1's PAIN-AD data, a power level of 0.80, and a 0.95 level of confidence, the power analysis revealed that 36 subjects would be required, which was just three more subjects than were included in the study. This is corroborated by the nearly significant interaction effect observed ($p = .06$) and suggests that further research is warranted, as these data strongly suggest that the PAIN-AD scale is capable of detecting decreases in patients' pain following intervention, a fact that would support the construct validity of the scale.

As Rater 2's PAIN-AD data were extremely similar to those of Rater 1, it is unsurprising that the power analysis revealed extremely similar findings. The power analysis based on Rater 2's data revealed that a sample of 38 subjects would be required, which was just six more subjects than were included in the study. As before, this finding is corroborated by the nearly significant interaction effect observed ($p = .06$) and suggests that further research is warranted.

CPOT

In order to examine the psychometric properties of the CPOT, Cronbach's alpha, 30-minute test-retest reliability (Pearson product-moment correlation), and interrater reliability (ICC[2,k]) were calculated (see Table 2).

Internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the CPOT revealed strong internal consistency (0.82-0.89).

Reliability. Once more, interrater reliability was excellent at baseline and after 30 minutes (0.99), proving the practicability of employing this tool in this work setting. Test-retest reliability was insufficient for participants without pain; test-retest scores reflected inadequate reliability (0.30-0.49) likely due to the CPOT not being utilized in the same manner as in previous studies.

Validity. Validity of the CPOT was established by examination of the scale's face validity, calculation of a multitrait matrix, and examinations of mean scores by condition and time.

In regard to face validity, a panel of experts in pain management ($n = 3$) at our institution reviewed the tool for face validity and found it to be excellent.

Examination of the item correlations between the PAIN-AD and CPOT via a multitrait matrix revealed promising findings, with fairly high correlations both between the PAIN-AD's individual questions as well as between the PAIN-AD's and the CPOT's questions, supporting the construct validity of the PAIN-AD (see Table 3). However, muscle tension appeared to contribute less to the scale, as evidenced by lower correlations between muscle tension and other CPOT items ($r = .38-.54, p < 0.05$ for all)

and between muscle tension and PAIN-AD items ($r = .23-.60$, two of five correlations not significant at the 0.05 level of confidence).

However, a repeated measures 2x2 ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction effect between time (pretest vs. posttest) and condition (pain intervention group vs. control group), Rater 1: $F(1,31) = 0.66, p = .42$, and Rater 2: $F(1,31) = 0.85, p = .36$. A statistically significant decrease in pain over time in the intervention group was theoretically expected and thus used as a condition for establishing construct validity.

Power analysis. Because statistically significant interaction effects between time (preintervention vs. postintervention) and intervention (pain intervention vs. control) were not observed despite a theoretical rationale expecting scores to decrease over time in the pain intervention group only and data matching the expected pattern (see Figures 2 and 3), it was decided to conduct a series of power analyses to determine the sample size that would have been needed in order to have an 80% chance of finding the observed interactions to be statistically significant.

Using the parameters (M, SD , correlations, etc.) from the analysis of Rater 1's CPOT data, a power level of 0.80, and a 0.95 level of confidence, the power analysis revealed that 836 subjects would be required, considerably more subjects than were included in the study. For Rater 2, the power analysis revealed a similarly large required sample size, with 586 subjects needed in order to have an 80% chance of treating an effect of the size observed in this study as significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. Together these data draw into question the construct validity of the CPOT, particularly compared to the PAIN-AD, which had results very close to statistical significance.

Discussion

This is the first study to examine the psychometrics of the PAIN-AD in older (age 65 years and older) CAM+ participants in general medical-surgical telemetry settings. While the PAIN-AD's utility has been examined in residential settings (Warden et al., 2003), our study supports the PAIN-AD as a valid and reliable tool for screening pain in CAM+ participants in these settings as well. Our study extends the work of previous researchers (Warden et al., 2003) and answers the call of Zwakhalen, Hamers, Abu-Saad, and Berger (2006) for additional analysis of the PAIN-AD's psychometric qualities. Appropriate pain screening will increase in importance as the population of geriatric participants with limited cognitive ability will grow to an estimated 83.7 million by the year 2050 (Ortman, Velkoff, & Hogan, 2014).

Mean change scores of the PAIN-AD and CPOT demonstrated similar results after pain interventions (see Figures 2-5). Ideally, two bedside providers were assessing for a statistically significant interaction effect between condition (pain intervention vs. no pain intervention) and time (preintervention vs. postintervention). The specific statistically significant interaction would show: (a) for the patients receiving a pain intervention, a reduction in pain 30 minutes after intervention and (b) for control participants receiving no pain intervention, no change in pain after 30 minutes. Unfortunately, this was not proven through the data. There was examination through four analyses (PAIN-AD with Raters 1 and 2 and CPOT with Raters 1 and 2); however, none of them reached statistical significance. It should be noted that visual inspection of the results as shown in Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5 do show pain scores moving in the direction a hypothesized had hypothesized (decreasing). The level and direction of correlations

between the PAIN-AD and the CPOT implies the scales measure similar but not identical constructs (see Table 3).

Reliability statistics were moderate to strong for the PAIN-AD in this study (interrater reliability, ICC = 0.99, and 30-minute test-retest reliability calculated with the Pearson product-moment correlation, $r = 0.72-0.73$). Discrepancies during the study were rare (two times) and these differences were settled by consensus. However, the CPOT, while demonstrating strong interrater reliability, exhibited faint 30-minute test-retest reliability ($r = 0.39-0.49$). Most likely, this finding relates to the manner of CPOT administration for the study. The CPOT was developed for use in the ICU and involves multiple observations. According to protocol, the patient is observed for 1 minute to establish a baseline score. Then, the patient is observed during a nociceptive procedure (e.g., turning, suctioning). Other observations occur prior to and during the peak effect of an analgesic intervention. The highest score observed during the observation period is the final score rating. Our intention in using the CPOT was for concurrent validity only, and its use was modified for such purposes. Analysis revealed abundant Cronbach's alpha for both scales (0.80-0.89), with single-item deletions making negligible improvements to the scale's internal consistency.

Pain screening in delirious geriatric populations is a challenging yet important endeavor (B. A. Ferrell & Ferrell, 1995). Attention to improving pain screening is critically important to improve patient care practices (Brown, 2004; Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2007). In this study, the data collectors received extensive training on the use of the tools, including face-to-face trainings and online modules related to the CPOT and PAIN-AD. However, this level of training may not be feasible in all clinical settings.

Nevertheless, continued training and reinforcement of concepts should be considered by supervising staff for improvement in patient care.

Our study supports previous research that suggests that screening for delirium by bedside providers may be suboptimal. Discrepancies in CAM identification were commonly identified by the two bedside providers. Accurate CAM identification is important not only for appropriate pain screening but also for reducing other deleterious sequelae such as increased length of stay and mortality (Inouye, 2006; Leslie, Marcantonio, Zhang, Leo-Summers, & Inouye, 2008; Rice et al., 2011; Waszynski, 2012). Future research may focus on identifying methods to improve the use of the CAM (Rice et al., 2011).

Caution is warranted in interpreting and applying the results of this study. The sample for this study was relatively homogenous and recruited from a single tertiary urban medical center. Thus, the findings may not be generalizable to a rural or more diverse population. However, the center provides care for over 14,000 inpatients annually and serves a diverse patient population (U.S. News and World Report, 2016). Most participants were assessed between 0700 a.m. and 1100 a.m., which may influence pain or delirium (Khachiyants, Trinkle, Son, & Kim, 2011) screenings. Cognition in geriatric populations may fluctuate over the course of the day according to Khachiyants et al. (2011). Future studies with larger samples may wish to examine the influence of time of day on the pain experiences of patients with delirium.

Screening for pain in the elderly delirious population must be a clinical priority to improve patient outcomes. Understanding the pain experiences of delirium positive patients remains difficult as fluctuating mental states can pose a challenge to appropriate

screening practices (Buffman, Hutt, Chang, Craine, & Snow, 2007). Pain screening in the cognitively impaired geriatric population who are unable to advocate for themselves has been a topic within healthcare for many years (B. A. Ferrell & Ferrell, 1995; Gélinas & Arbour, 2009; Warden et al., 2003; Zwakhalen et al., 2006), yet our ability to provide appropriate screening followed by timely interventions remains in question. There is a clear association between a history of dementia and the development of delirium in acutely hospitalized participants. Therefore, it should be argued that pain should be assessed more often than not through a nonverbal scale within this population.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics

Variable	<i>n</i>	(%)	Mean	(range, <i>SD</i>)
Gender				
Male	16	(45.7)		
Female	19	(54.3)		
Race				
Black	4	(11.1)		
White	27	(75.0)		
Hispanic	1	(2.8)		
Other	4	(11.1)		
Ethnicity				
Not Hispanic	35	(97.2)		
Hispanic	1	(2.8)		
Actively Infected				
Yes	16	(45.7)		
No	19	(54.3)		
Presence of Sedating Medications				
Yes	5	(14.3)		
No	30	(85.7)		
History of Dementia				
Yes	25	(69.4)		
No	11	(30.6)		
Recently Required Anesthesia				
Yes	5	(13.9)		
No	31	(86.1)		
Demographics				
Age			86.14	(65-96, 8.49)
Length of Stay			5.17	(1-20, 4.53)
Days				
Pain at Baseline				
PAIN-AD			2.93	(0-10, 2.84)
CPOT			2.21	(0-8, 2.38)

Note. *n* = 35-36.

Table 2

Psychometric Properties of CPOT and PAIN-AD

	PAIN-AD		CPOT	
	Baseline	30-Minute Follow-Up	Baseline	30-Minute Follow-Up
Cronbach's Alpha ^a	.80-.83	.81-.87	.82	.87-.89
Interrater Reliability (ICC Two-Way, Random)	.99 ^b	.99 ^b	.99	.99
30-Minute Test-Retest Reliability ^a	.72-.73		.30-.49	

Note. $n = 16-36$.

^aRange represents the maximum and minimum α obtained by two raters.

^bScore was rounded down, as rounding up implies perfect reliability.

Table 3

Baseline Inter-Item Correlations Between CPOT and PAIN-AD Scores (N = 36)

		CPOT					PAIN-AD				
		1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.
CPOT	1. Overall Score	-									
	2. Facial Expression	.82***	-								
	3. Body Movements	.84***	.56***	-							
	4. Vocalization	.84***	.75***	.53***	-						
	5. Muscle Tension	.72***	.38*	.54***	.42*	-					
PAIN-AD	6. Overall Score	.87***	.84***	.62***	.84***	.50**	-				
	7. Breathing	.57***	.50**	.45**	.54***	.35*	.70***	-			
	8. Negative Vocalization	.67***	.62***	.49**	.78***	.23	.83***	.53***	-		
	9. Facial Expression	.84***	.76***	.61***	.81***	.50**	.85***	.50**	.68***	-	
	10. Body Language	.73***	.66***	.53***	.60***	.60***	.74***	.41*	.50**	.56***	-
	11. Consolability	.55***	.61***	.34*	.54***	.25	.72***	.24	.53***	.55***	.48**

* $p \leq .05$. ** $p \leq .01$. *** $p \leq .001$.

Figure 2. PAIN-AD score by time and condition Rater 1.

Figure 3. PAIN-AD score by time and condition Rater 2.

Figure 4. CPOT score by time and condition Rater 1.

Figure 5. CPOT score by time and condition Rater 2.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR DELIRIUM AND PAIN ASSESSMENT

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
<p>Determine the sensitivity and specificity of the CAM in the diagnosis of delirium in acutely hospitalized geriatric participants</p> <p>(Laurila et al., 2002)</p>	<p>Cross-sectional study</p> <p>CAM</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 81</p> <p>Age > 70 years, noncomatose</p> <p>Acute care geriatric ward in Finland</p>	<p>Assessments performed within a 6-hour time period</p> <p>Diagnostic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>DSM-III, III-R, IV</i> • ICD-10 • CAM <p>Screening tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MMSE • Adult Intelligence Scale 	<p>Demographics: 75.3% female, 27.2% > 85 years old, 45.7% widowed, 42% attended primary school or less education, 79% living alone, 43.2% had underlying dementia, 14.8% has diagnosis of depression, 3.7% had psychosis</p> <p>Delirium identified in 9%-42% of sample</p> <p>Delirium identification through: CAM—42% <i>DSM-IV</i>—39.5% <i>DSM-III-R</i>—25.9% <i>DSM-III</i>—24.7% ICD—10 9.9%</p> <p>CAM specificity—0.63 & 0.84 CAM sensitivity—0.81-0.86</p> <p>CAM-subjects are true negatives when compared to <i>DSM</i> or ICD delirium criteria</p>	<p>Conclusions: CAM is a useful screening tool for detection of delirium</p> <p>Formal delirium diagnosis should be confirmed according to formalized criteria and not on the basis of a positive CAM</p> <p>Limitations: Findings could vary and might not be applicable for all participant types such as postoperative participants</p>

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
Assess the diagnostic validity of CAM using the sensitivity and specificity methods (Lemiengre et al., 2006)	Prospective descriptive study CAM Cognitive status	<i>N</i> = 258 Age > 70 years, verbal Acute geriatric ward in Belgium	Assessments performed by bedside nurses, then by two researchers Diagnostic criteria: <i>DSM-IV</i> Screening tools: • CAM • MMSE	Demographics: Age 82.6 +/-5.9%, female 62.4%, male 37.6%, presence of cognitive impairment 54.1%, with dementia 12.0% 774 observations in 258 participants Sensitivity of bedside nursing rating 23.8% (low) Specificity of 97.7% Then 41 additional cases falsely diagnosed with delirium Specificity 90.8% (bedside nurses did not over identify delirium) Sensitivity of 66.7% (bedside nurses' difficulty in recognizing symptoms) NPV 94.8% for specificity method (high) NPV 97.5% for sensitivity method (high) PPV 41.7% for specificity method (low) PPV 33.7% for sensitivity method (moderate) Kappa statistics 0.33-0.51 poor to fair agreement, exceeding chance	Conclusions: Bedside nurses are proficient at identifying participants without delirium Bedside nurses exemplify poor to moderate ability screening for delirium in hospitalized participants. Difficulty recognizing deliriums acute onset, fluctuations, and altered level of consciousness. Limitations: No physicians to validate diagnosis of delirium Not all observations were independent of one another Bedside nurses not given enough formal education on how to use the CAM prior to study

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
Comparison of the CNPI and PAIN-AD instruments for reliability and validity in long-term care facilities	A cross-sectional descriptive study Pain	<i>N</i> = 66 Age > 65 years, moderate to severe pain 1 week prior to baseline data collection, non-hospice	Two nurse researchers and two graduate nurses who received education on how to use CNPI and PAIN-AD instruments Participants unable to state pain were videotaped at rest and during movement with assistance from a CNA	Demographics: Female 88%; mean age of 89; and mean CPS 3.9, indicating participants were moderately to severely cognitively impaired CNPI: At rest mean 0.9 (<i>SD</i> = 2.0) and 0.8 (<i>SD</i> = 1.7) for each rater and with movement 1.9 (<i>SD</i> = 2.2) and 2.0 (<i>SD</i> = 1.6) for each rater Cronbach's alpha at rest .97 and .92 Cronbach's alpha with movement .74 and .90	Conclusions: Dedicated pain assessments should be completed in addition to use of these tools More pain is observed with the CNPI and PAIN-AD with movement
Effectiveness of a pain management algorithm in nursing homes		14 nursing homes in the United States	Average videotaping time of 12 minutes Assessment of videotaped pain by nurses who viewed tapes in random order	Kappa scores 0.43 for at rest and 0.25 with movement More positive itemization with movement	Limitations: No examination of reliability rating over time
(Ersek, Herr, Neradilek, Buck, & Black, 2010)			Information extraction from the Minimum data set Screening tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IPT • CNPI • PAIN-AD • CPS • PAS 	PAIN-AD: At rest 0.2 (<i>SD</i> = 0.6) and 0.4 (<i>SD</i> = 1.0) for each rater and with movement 1.7 (<i>SD</i> = 2.1) and 2.4 (<i>SD</i> = 2.1) for each rater Cronbach's alpha at rest .72 (for Rater 2) and -.04 for Rater 1 (poor internal consistency) and Cronbach's alpha with movement .70 and .72	

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
				Kappa statistic 0.54 for PAIN-AD with movement and 0.31 for at rest Construct validity support as increased scores with movement than at rest for both raters	
Identification of delirium in the ER with the DTS and Brief bCAM (Han et al., 2013)	A prospective observational study	<i>N</i> = 406 Age > 65 years, < 12 hours in the ED, English speaking, verbal, intact vision and hearing, able to follow simple commands Large academic tertiary care hospital in the ED in the United States	A student research and physician performed the DTS and bCAM on eligible participants; one rater performed the DTS and bCAM while the other observed Diagnostic tools: <i>DSM-IV</i> Screening tools: • DTS • bCAM	Demographics: Median age 73.5, sex 49.8% female, diagnosis of dementia 5.9%, emergency severity score > 2 65% Out of 406 participants, 50 received a diagnosis of delirium DTS: Rater physician and researcher had a negative likelihood ratio of 0.04 (a negative DTS ruled out delirium). <i>K</i> was 0.79 indicating good inter-observer reliability bCAM: Rater physician and researcher had positive likelihood ratio of 19.9 and 25.2 (a positive bCAM strongly increased the likelihood of delirium) <i>K</i> was 0.88, indicating excellent inter-observer reliability Research assistants performed DTS followed by physician; bCAM sensitivity of 84.0%	Conclusions: A two-step approach to assess delirium in the ED using the DTS and bCAM could be helpful in more appropriate diagnosis Limitations: Does not account for drugs administered in ED which can contribute to delirium onset Difficult to generalize without further research

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
				<p>Research assistants performed both DTS and bCAM; the combination was 78% sensitive and 97.2% specific</p> <p>Physicians performed the DTS and bCAM; it was 82% sensitive and 95.8% specific</p>	
Development of PAIN-AD to detect pain in nonverbal geriatric participants (Warden et al., 2003)	An observational study	<p><i>N</i> = 19 (for tool validation)</p> <p><i>N</i> = 25 (for QI to show tool effectiveness)</p> <p>Diagnosis of dementia, no planned discharge, inability to report pain discomfort, a proxy/decision maker identified in chart</p> <p>Location: Bedford, MA</p>	<p>PAIN-AD and DS-DAT administered by two raters. Observed during three separate occasions, at rest, during pleasant activity, and during caregiving</p> <p>PAIN-AD measurement of 25 participants before and 30 minutes after PRN med administration</p> <p>Screening tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MMSE • BANS-S • VAS • DS-DAT • PAIN-AD 	<p>Demographics: Mean age 78, all suffered from dementia</p> <p>Three observations: 1.3 +/- 1.3 during no stimulation, 1.0 +/- 1.3 during pleasant activity or rest, and 3.1 +/- 1.7 during an unpleasant event, <i>p</i> < 0.001</p> <p>PRN medication effectiveness based upon PAIN-AD 6.7 +/- prior to PRN administration and 1.8 +/- 30 minutes after PRN pain medication, <i>p</i> < 0.001</p> <p>Cronbach's alpha 0.70 for the new scale (less than desired)</p>	<p>Conclusions: Useful tool for measuring pain in dementia participants</p> <p>Short and easy to use pain identification tool for advanced dementia participants</p> <p>Limitations: Abnormal distribution of pain scores</p>

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
Validation of CPOT in English for assessment of pain in nonverbal participants (Gélinas & Johnston, 2007)	Crossover observational study	<i>N</i> = 55 > 18 years old, admitted to the ICU, ventilated, conscious or unconscious Location: Montreal, Canada	ICU nurses assessed participants during a nociceptive procedure and a non-nociceptive procedure; results compared to study coordinators Screening tools: • CPOT • FPT • Self-report	Demographics: Mean age 60, 32 male, 23 female, and 19 with head trauma Interrater reliability 0.80-0.93 between PI and critical care nurse Scores correlated with self-report CPOT score > 3 showed 66.7% sensitivity and 83.3% specificity	Conclusions: The CPOT proved to be valid when translated from French to English The CPOT is valid and reliable in the critical care population for pain assessment Limitations: Nursing staff may have anticipated increased pain behavior during nociceptive procedures
Evaluate the utility of a distress tool in the dementia population used in conjunction with the PAIN-AD tool (Jordan et al., 2012)	A prospective observational study	<i>N</i> = 79 Established clinical diagnosis of dementia, screen with the CDR—a score of 3 or more were included Location in the United Kingdom	PAIN-AD or DisDat used to assess participant during observation by a nurse or researcher Screening tools: • CDR • PAIN-AD • DisDat • PACA	Demographics: 72% female, mean age of 82, 53% with diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease, 29% had vascular dementia, 11% had mixed AD and vascular dementia, and 4% had dementia with Lewy body 79 participants; 13 identified to have pain Improvement in both PAIN-AD and DisDat after changes in management, <i>p</i> = 0.008	Conclusion: The PAIN-AD tool used with the DisDat tool can be used as a barometer for screening and sequential improvement of pain after a given intervention Limitations: PAIN-AD has low specificity; therefore, it can pick up false positives No established interrater reliability for DisDat tool

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
Validate the CPOT in participants > 18 years old (Gélinas et al., 2006)	A prospective observational study	<i>N</i> = 105 18 years old, admitted for cardiac surgery, understood French, in the ICU postsurgery, could hear, could see Study took place in the ICU at a cardiology health center in Canada	Three assessments completed over three testing periods for a total of nine pain assessments using the CPOT (T1-T9) One critical care nurse and one researcher completed the assessments Screening tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CPOT • CAM-ICU 	Demographics: Mean age of 60, 83% female, and 22% male 1st testing: CPOT scores were higher during positioning 2nd testing: CPOT scores were higher during positioning procedure 3rd testing: CPOT scores were similar to the second testing Interrater reliability: Researcher and critical care nurse completed CPOT assessments weighted κ coefficients moderate to high on all assessments	Conclusions: Postoperative pain was higher for participants during movement procedures Limitations: Two people conducted assessments; increasing the number of people doing assessment could have increased the strength of interrater reliability Participants who were delirious were excluded from the study; it would have been helpful to identify if this tool was a good measure of pain in the elderly delirious population
Measurement of nurse's recognition of delirium in hospitalized elderly adults through the use of the CAM (Rice et al., 2011)	A prospective, descriptive design Model of information processed theory	<i>N</i> = 170 65 years old, fluency in English, able to read, able to write Study conducted in the United States at a large tertiary care center	Completion of the CAM by nurse one time per 12-hour shift Screening tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIADL • Jaeger near-point vision test • the whisper hearing test • MMSE • CAM 	Demographics: Mean age of 75.8 years, near equal gender distribution, 75% had baseline cognitive impairment consistent with dementia Delirium detected in 12 out of 170 participants (7%) Nurses recognized delirium in three out of the 12 participants (25%) Sensitivities of nurses' ratings for delirium were low	Conclusion: Nurses are poor detectors of delirium at the bedside as indicated by this study where delirium was not recognized in 75% of cases Limitations: Lower incidence of delirium in target population than was hypothesized

Purpose & Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions & Limitations
			Interviews by researchers using the MMSE and the CAM every other day until delirium was detected or participant discharged	The PPV for nurses' ratings for delirium using the CAM was low Nurses' recognition of delirium compared to the researcher, $p < .0001$ 100% agreement when delirium was not present	

Note. bCAM = brief Confusion Assessment Method, BIADL = Barthel Index of Activities of Daily Living, CAM = Confusion Assessment Method, CAM-ICU = Confusion Assessment Method for the intensive care unit, CDR = Clinical Dementia Rating, CNA = clinical nursing assistant, CNPI = Checklist of Non-Verbal Pain Indicators, CPOT = Critical Care Pain Observation Tool, CPS = Cognitive Performance Scale, DisDat = Disability Distress Assessment, *DSM* = *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, DTS = Delirium Triage Screen, ED = emergency department, ER = emergency room, FPT = Functional Performance Test, ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient, ICD = International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, ICU = intensive care unit, IPT = Iowa Pain Thermometer, MMSE = Mini-Mental State Exam, NOPPAIN = Non-Communicative Participants Pain Assessment Instrument, NPV = negative predictive value, NRS = Numeric Rating Scale, PACA = Palliative Care Assessment Tool, PAIN-AD = Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia Scale, PAS = Pittsburg Agitation Scale, PI = Principle Investigator PPV = positive predictive value, PRN = as needed, VDS = Verbal Descriptive Scale.

APPENDIX B**HARTFORD LINK FOR PERMSSION TO USE CAM****Permission for Cam****Meyer, Jeannette M.**

To: Ferolito, Michelle
Cc: 'joy.goebel@csulb.edu'; Ramirez, Diana

Wednesday, February 04, 2015 9:48 AM

[http://consultgerirn.org/uploads/File/Confusion%20Assessment%20Method%20\(CAM\).pdf](http://consultgerirn.org/uploads/File/Confusion%20Assessment%20Method%20(CAM).pdf)

Jeannette (Jeannie) Meyer, RN, MSN, CCRN, CCNS, PCCN, ACHPN
Clinical Nurse Specialist for Palliative Care
Assistant Clinical Professor UCLA School of Nursing
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Direct line # 424 259 8161
Cell #310 210-9270
Pager#310206-8477 Extension 96023

APPENDIX C**PERMISSION FOR USE OF PAIN-AD****Thank You For Your Order!**

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APPENDIX D
PERMISSION TO USE CPOT

April 22, 2015

Michelle Ferolito, RN, MSN, GNP
1720 Newport Avenue, Unit 18
Long Beach, CA 90804

Dear Michelle:

Thank you for your request. We hereby grant permission to reproduce the material (the Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool, or CPOT) at no charge subject to the following conditions:

1. Suitable acknowledgment to the original source is made as follows wherever possible:
"Gélinas C, Fillion L, Puntillo KA, Viens C, Fortier M. Validation of the Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool in adult patients. *Am J Crit Care*. 2006;15(4):420-427. Table 1.
Available at: <http://ajcc.aacnjournals.org/content/15/4/420.short>. ©2006 American Association of Critical-Care Nurses. Used with permission."
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Sincerely,

Michael Muscat
Publishing Manager
American Association of Critical-Care Nurses

APPENDIX E

FLYER POSTED ON NURSING UNITS

PAIN ASSESSMENT IN THE DELIRIOUS PARTICIPANT A CLOSER OBSERVATION

Study to take place from the months of September to December
Nursing staff to inform researchers of CAM (+) Participants when
Asked

APPENDIX F**EMAIL ANNOUNCEMENT TO NURSING STAFF****PAIN SCREENING IN THE DELIRIOUS GERIATRIC PARTICIPANT**

Dear Acute Care Geriatric Nurses and Clinical Care Partners,

You are being invited to participate in a research study on pain screening in the delirious geriatric participant. The aim of this study is to establish the reliability and validity of the PAIN-AD tool in this population.

This research will require floor nurses to identify participants who are confusion assessment method (CAM) positive. Staff members will identify CAM+ participants at the start of the shift and inform the researchers (Michelle Ferolito, Ashwini Prasad, and Darya Ratliff).

For CAM+ participants, the PAIN AD will then be performed by two researchers. If the PAIN AD score is ≥ 3 , the nurse or clinical care partner will be asked to turn the participant, administer heat, provide an analgesic, or other appropriate nursing intervention. For participants with a PAIN AD score <3 , no treatment will be provided. A second pain screening will occur 30 minutes after the initial screening. You will not be responsible for the pain assessments and your participants may or may not be included in this study.

The results from this study will be provided to the staff and may be published in a journal. The results may also be presented at professional conferences.

We are attaching a consent form. We are hoping you will participate in this effort to improve pain screening among our geriatric participant population. To participate in this study, please sign the attached consent and return it to the mailbox of Michelle Ferolito on 5NW in the enclosed envelop. An extra consent form is attached for your records.

Your participation is entirely voluntary and will not affect your employment.

For any questions about this study please contact: Michelle Ferolito RN MSN DNP(c) at mferolito@mednet.ucla.edu or by cell @ (617) 904-8280.

Respectfully,

Michelle Ferolito RN MNS DNP(c), Co-Principal Investigator
Edith Matesic RN MSN DNP CNO, Principal Investigator

APPENDIX G
DATA EXTRACTION TOOL

Cover Sheet

Participant Name: _____

Participant Medical Record Number: _____

Participant Identifier: _____ (five digit code: MMDDYR and sequential letter)

Participant Identifier _____ Researcher Initials: _____ Date: _____

Data Tool**PAIN SCREENING IN THE DELIRIOUS PARTICIPANT**

Electronic Chart Review	<p>1. Confirm CAM (+) Participants</p> <p>2. Have a history of pain (i.e. arthritis)?</p> <p>3. Has this participant recently had a procedure, which required anesthesia?</p> <p>4. Is this participant actively infected? (e.g., WBC > 12, Temp > 38.0, HR > 100, RR > 20)?</p> <p>5. Is the participant taking benzodiazepines?</p> <p>6. History of Dementia?</p>	<p>1. Yes/No</p> <p>2. Yes/No Specify_____</p> <p>3. Yes/No Specify_____</p> <p>4. Yes/No Specify_____</p> <p>5. Yes/No Specify_____</p> <p>6. Yes/No</p>
	1. Age	_____
	<p>1. Sex</p> <p>2. Ethnicity</p>	<p>A. Male B. Female</p> <p>A. White B. Black C. Hispanic D. Pacific Islander E. Other</p>

Time Spent in Hospital	1. Length of Stay	_____
Date Time Delirium Identified		
Type of pain treatment		
Diagnosis	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____	

Assessment 1 Time started _____ Time Ended _____ Consensus Score _____
 Ethnicity AA _____ CAUS _____ OTHER _____
 Participant Identifier _____ Researcher Initials: _____ Date: _____

Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia Scale (PAINAD)

Instructions: Observe the patient for five minutes before scoring his or her behaviors. Score the behaviors according to the following chart. Definitions of each item are provided on the following page. The patient can be observed under different conditions (e.g., at rest, during a pleasant activity, during caregiving, after the administration of pain medication).

Behavior	0	1	2	Score
Breathing Independent of vocalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Normal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occasional labored breathing Short period of hyperventilation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Noisy labored breathing Long period of hyperventilation Cheyne-Stokes respirations 	
Negative vocalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occasional moan or groan Low-level speech with a negative or disapproving quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repeated troubled calling out Loud moaning or groaning Crying 	
Facial expression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smiling or inexpressive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sad Frightened Frown 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facial grimacing 	
Body language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relaxed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tense Distressed pacing Fidgeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigid Fists clenched Knees pulled up Pulling or pushing away Striking out 	
Consolability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No need to console 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distracted or reassured by voice or touch 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unable to console, distract, or reassure 	
TOTAL SCORE				

(Warden et al., 2003)

Scoring:

The total score ranges from 0-10 points. A possible interpretation of the scores is: 1-3=mild pain; 4-6=moderate pain; 7-10=severe pain. These ranges are based on a standard 0-10 scale of pain, but have not been substantiated in the literature for this tool.

Source:

Warden V, Hurley AC, Volicer L. Development and psychometric evaluation of the Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia (PAINAD) scale. *J Am Med Dir Assoc.* 2003;4(1):9-15.

Assessment 1 Time started _____ Time Ended _____ Consensus Score _____
 Participant Identifier _____ Researcher Initials: _____ Date: _____

The Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool (CPOT)
 (Gélinas et al., 2006)

Indicator	Score	Description	
Facial expression <p>Caroline Arbour, RN, B.Sc., PhD(student) School of Nursing, McGill University</p>	Relaxed, neutral	0	No muscle tension observed
	Tense	1	Presence of frowning, brow lowering, orbit tightening and levator contraction or any other change (e.g. opening eyes or tearing during nociceptive procedures)
	Grimacing	2	All previous facial movements plus eyelid tightly closed (the patient may present with mouth open or biting the endotracheal tube)
Body movements	Absence of movements or normal position	0	Does not move at all (doesn't necessarily mean absence of pain) or normal position (movements not aimed toward the pain site or not made for the purpose of protection)
	Protection	1	Slow, cautious movements, touching or rubbing the pain site, seeking attention through movements
	Restlessness/Agitation	2	Pulling tube, attempting to sit up, moving limbs/thrashing, not following commands, striking at staff, trying to climb out of bed
Compliance with the ventilator (intubated patients)	Tolerating ventilator or movement	0	Alarms not activated, easy ventilation
	Coughing but tolerating	1	Coughing, alarms may be activated but stop spontaneously
	Fighting ventilator	2	Asynchrony: blocking ventilation, alarms frequently activated
OR Vocalization (extubated patients)	Talking in normal tone or no sound	0	Talking in normal tone or no sound
	Sighing, moaning	1	Sighing, moaning
	Crying out, sobbing	2	Crying out, sobbing
Muscle tension Evaluation by passive flexion and extension of upper limbs when patient is at rest or evaluation when patient is being turned	Relaxed	0	No resistance to passive movements
	Tense, rigid	1	Resistance to passive movements
	Very tense or rigid	2	Strong resistance to passive movements or incapacity to complete them
TOTAL		___ / 8	

Assessment 2 Time started _____ Time Ended _____ Consensus Score _____
 Participant Identifier _____ Researcher Initials: _____ Date: _____

Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia Scale (PAINAD)

Instructions: Observe the patient for five minutes before scoring his or her behaviors. Score the behaviors according to the following chart. Definitions of each item are provided on the following page. The patient can be observed under different conditions (e.g., at rest, during a pleasant activity, during caregiving, after the administration of pain medication).

Behavior	0	1	2	Score
Breathing Independent of vocalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Normal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occasional labored breathing Short period of hyperventilation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Noisy labored breathing Long period of hyperventilation Cheyne-Stokes respirations 	
Negative vocalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occasional moan or groan Low-level speech with a negative or disapproving quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repeated troubled calling out Loud moaning or groaning Crying 	
Facial expression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smiling or inexpressive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sad Frightened Frown 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facial grimacing 	
Body language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relaxed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tense Distressed pacing Fidgeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigid Fists clenched Knees pulled up Pulling or pushing away Striking out 	
Consolability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No need to console 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distracted or reassured by voice or touch 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unable to console, distract, or reassure 	
TOTAL SCORE				

(Warden et al., 2003)

Scoring:

The total score ranges from 0-10 points. A possible interpretation of the scores is: 1-3=mild pain; 4-6=moderate pain; 7-10=severe pain. These ranges are based on a standard 0-10 scale of pain, but have not been substantiated in the literature for this tool.

Source:

Warden V, Hurley AC, Volicer L. Development and psychometric evaluation of the Pain Assessment in Advanced Dementia (PAINAD) scale. *J Am Med Dir Assoc.* 2003;4(1):9-15.

Assessment 2 Time started _____ Time Ended _____ Consensus Score _____
 Participant Identifier _____ Researcher Initials: _____ Date: _____

The Critical-Care Pain Observation Tool (CPOT)

(Gélinas et al., 2006)

Indicator	Score	Description		
Facial expression <p>Caroline Arbour, RN, B.Sc., PhD(student) School of Nursing, McGill University</p>	Relaxed, neutral	0	No muscle tension observed	
	Tense	1	Presence of frowning, brow lowering, orbit tightening and levator contraction or any other change (e.g. opening eyes or tearing during nociceptive procedures)	
	Grimacing	2	All previous facial movements plus eyelid tightly closed (the patient may present with mouth open or biting the endotracheal tube)	
Body movements	Absence of movements or normal position	0	Does not move at all (doesn't necessarily mean absence of pain) or normal position (movements not aimed toward the pain site or not made for the purpose of protection)	
	Protection	1	Slow, cautious movements, touching or rubbing the pain site, seeking attention through movements	
	Restlessness/Agitation	2	Pulling tube, attempting to sit up, moving limbs/thrashing, not following commands, striking at staff, trying to climb out of bed	
Compliance with the ventilator (intubated patients)	Tolerating ventilator or movement	0	Alarms not activated, easy ventilation	
	Coughing but tolerating	1	Coughing, alarms may be activated but stop spontaneously	
	Fighting ventilator	2	Asynchrony: blocking ventilation, alarms frequently activated	
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	Sighing, moaning	1	Sighing, moaning	
	Crying out, sobbing	2	Crying out, sobbing	
Muscle tension	Relaxed	0	No resistance to passive movements	
	Evaluation by passive flexion and extension of upper limbs when patient is at rest or evaluation when patient is being turned	Tense, rigid	1	Resistance to passive movements
	Very tense or rigid	2	Strong resistance to passive movements or incapacity to complete them	
TOTAL		___ / 8		

APPENDIX H

UCLA IRB APPROVAL LETTER

Page 1 of 2

University of California Los Angeles
11000 Kinross Avenue, Suite 211
Los Angeles, CA 90095-1694

<http://ohrpp.research.ucla.edu>
GC-IRB: (310) 825-7122
M-IRB: (310) 825-5344

APPROVAL NOTICE
New Study

DATE:	7/22/2015
TO:	EDITH MATESIC MEDCTR-SANTA MONICA HOSPITAL
FROM:	JAMES MC GOUGH, MD Chair, MIRB3
RE:	IRB#15-000763 Pain Screening in the Delirious Geriatric Patient Version: Version #3 6/11/2015

The UCLA Institutional Review Board (UCLA IRB) has approved the above-referenced study. UCLA's Federalwide Assurance (FWA) with Department of Health and Human Services is FWA00004642.

Submission and Review Information

Type of Review	Expedited Review
Approval Date	7/22/2015
Expiration Date of the Study	7/21/2018

Regulatory Determinations

– **Three Year Extended Approval** - The UCLA IRB has determined that this study meets the criteria for a 3 year extended approval. (For reference, please see the OHRPP guidance document "Extended Approval for Minimal Risk Research Not Subject to Federal Oversight" at http://ora.research.ucla.edu/OHRPP/Documents/Policy/4/Extended_Approval.pdf)

– **Waiver of Informed Consent** - The UCLA IRB waived the requirement for informed consent under 45 CFR 46.116(d) for the entire study.

<https://webirb.research.ucla.edu/WEBIRB/Doc/0/OH8HNIPSMEQKV36IJHNNN1AOAF/...> 7/27/2015

APPENDIX I

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH, IRB APPROVAL

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: December 8, 2015

TO: Michelle Ferolito, Rn, MSN, DNP(c)

FROM: California State University, Long Beach (IRB)

PROJECT TITLE: [832677-2] PAIN SCREENING IN THE DELIRIOUS PATIENT

REFERENCE #: 16-164s

SUBMISSION TYPE: Revision

ACTION: APPROVED

APPROVAL DATE: December 4, 2015

EXPIRATION DATE: December 3, 2016

REVIEW TYPE: Administrative

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Your application is approved. The requested modifications have been received, reviewed, and accepted.

Approval is for a period of one year and conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy. If you would like to continue this research after this one year period, please submit a renewal application and an annual report to the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs two months prior to your expiration date of December 3, 2016.

1. You are required to inform the Director or Senior Associate Director, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, in writing (email is acceptable) or through IRBNet within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
2. You may not change any aspect of your research procedure involving human subjects without written permission from the Director, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs or the Chair of the IRB. Please use the Protocol Modification Form on IRBNet to request any changes.
3. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.

APPENDIX J

SMUCLA NURSING RESEARCH PRACTICE COUNSEL APPROVAL LETTER

NPRC Study Approval - Pain-AD Study

Miller, Pamela S.

 Actions

To: Ferolito, Michelle; Matesic, Edith K.

Attachments: NPRC Approval Letter 8-25-15.pdf (63 KB) [Open as Web Page]

Tuesday, August 25, 2015 5:56 PM

- You replied on 8/25/2015 5:59 PM.

Dear Dr. Matesic and Ms. Ferolito,

The Nursing Practice Research Council (NPRC) and Ms. Heidi Crooks, Interim Chief Nurse Executive, approved your research study entitled **"Pain Screening in the Delirious Geriatric Patient"** for conduct at Santa Monica UCLA Medical Center.

You will find a copy of the NPRC approval letter attached for your records. You will be able to conduct your study with IRB approval.

Your study seems very innovative, and we will be very interested in hearing about the results.

Please let me know if you have any additional questions or need further assistance.

Best,

Pamela Miller, PhD, RN, ACNP, CNS

Nurse Scientist | Research and Evidence-Based Practice Program
UCLA Health | Department of Nursing Research and Education
10920 Wilshire Blvd., Suite 1030 | Los Angeles, CA 90095-7328
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